

Several Spectrally Non-Arbitrary Ray Patterns of Order 4

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Abstract—A matrix is called a ray pattern matrix if its entries are either 0 or a ray in complex plane which originates from 0. A ray pattern A of order n is called spectrally arbitrary if the complex matrices in the ray pattern class of A give rise to all possible n th degree complex polynomial. Otherwise, it is said to be spectrally non-arbitrary ray pattern. We call that a spectrally arbitrary ray pattern A of order n is minimally spectrally arbitrary if any nonzero entry of A is replaced, then A is not spectrally arbitrary. In this paper, we find that is not spectrally arbitrary when n equals to 4 for any θ which is greater than or equal to 0 and less than or equal to n . In this article, we give several ray patterns $A(\theta)$ of order n that are not spectrally arbitrary for some θ which is greater than or equal to 0 and less than or equal to n . by using the nilpotent-Jacobi method. One example is given in our paper.

Keywords—Spectrally arbitrary, Nilpotent matrix, Ray patterns, sign patterns.

I. INTRODUCTION

A $n \times n$ ray pattern A is a matrix with entries a_{ij} from

$$\{re^{i\theta} : r > 0\} \cup \{0\}$$

For brevity, we denote a ray $re^{i\theta}$ simply by $e^{i\theta}$. It is easy to verify that for two rays $e^{i\theta_1}$ and $e^{i\theta_2}$, if $\theta_1 - \theta_2 = 2k\pi$ where k is an integer number, then

$$e^{i\theta_1} = e^{i\theta_2}; \quad (1)$$

otherwise, $e^{i\theta_1} \neq e^{i\theta_2}$. For two rays $e^{i\theta_1}$ and $e^{i\theta_2}$, multiplication, division and addition are performed obviously. The product and quotient are given as:

$$e^{i\theta_1} e^{i\theta_2} = e^{i(\theta_1 + \theta_2)} \quad (2)$$

and

$$e^{i\theta_1} / e^{i\theta_2} = e^{i(\theta_1 - \theta_2)}. \quad (3)$$

θ_1 and θ_2 differ by a multiple of 2π , then $e^{i\theta_1} + e^{i\theta_2} = e^{i\theta_1}$.

The sum of two distinct rays $e^{i\theta_1}$ and $e^{i\theta_2}$ is either a straight

line through the origin or an open sector in the complex plane with vertex at the origin (when the two rays are opposite in direction). We denote $\#$ by any sum of rays where at least two of the rays are distinct. It is easy to verify that

$$e^{i\theta} + \# = \#, \quad e^{i\theta} \# = \# \\ 0 + \# = \#, \quad 0 \# = 0, \quad \# + \# = \#, \quad \# \# = \#.$$

Let $z = x + iy$ be a non-zero complex number and $r = |z| = \sqrt{x^2 + y^2}$, then we get $x = r \cos \theta$, $y = r \sin \theta$, where θ is the angle made by z with the positive x -axis. Therefore, θ is unique up to the addition of a multiple of 2π radians. We call the number θ satisfying the above pair of equations and argument of z and denote it by $\arg z$. The ray pattern class of an $n \times n$ ray pattern A , denoted by $Q(A)$, is the set of $n \times n$ complex matrices given by

$$\{B : [b_{pq}] \in M_n(\mathbb{C}) : b_{pq} = 0 \text{ if } a_{pq} = 0; \\ \arg b_{pq} = \arg a_{pq} \text{ otherwise}\}.$$

An $n \times n$ ray pattern A is said to be spectrally arbitrary if given any monic n th degree polynomial $f(x)$ with coefficients from \mathbb{C} , there exists a matrix $B \in Q(A)$ having characteristic polynomial $f(x)$. A spectrally arbitrary ray pattern A is said to be minimally spectrally arbitrary if any nonzero entry of A is replaced by zero, then it is not spectrally arbitrary.

The question of the existence of spectrally arbitrary sign patterns, that is, sign patterns that allow the realization of every self-conjugate spectrum, arose in [1]. In this paper, the nilpotent-Jacobi method for showing that a sign pattern was developed and all its superpatterns are spectrally arbitrary and a conjunction that a particular family of tridiagonal patterns is spectrally arbitrary was given. Since that time there have been many papers on this topic (see, for example, [2]-[7]) and several families of spectrally arbitrary patterns have been presented and general properties of spectrally arbitrary patterns have been studied ([8-11]). In [12], Britz et al. showed that every irreducible, spectrally arbitrary sign pattern of order n must have at least $2n-1$ nonzeros and they also gave families of patterns that have exactly $2n$ nonzeros. This result is easily extended to zero-nonzero patterns over \mathbb{R} and \mathbb{C} . In [13], the problem of classifying the spectrally arbitrary zero-nonzero patterns over \mathbb{R} is studied and all $n \times n$ spectrally arbitrary zero-nonzero patterns are classified when $n \geq 4$. This article

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presented the idea that identifies the maximum number of nonzero entries such that a zero-nonzero pattern with maximum number of nonzeros is spectrally arbitrary. In [14], DeAlba et al. studied properties of reducible, spectrally arbitrary sign and zero-nonzero patterns over \mathbb{R} . Recently, McDonald and Stuart [19] described a method for proving an irreducible ray pattern with exactly $3n$ non-zeros and its superpatterns are spectrally. From that time there have many articles on this topic (see, for example, [15]-[18]).

II. THE NILPOTENT-JACOBI METHOD

In [9], Drew et al. gave a method of establishing that a sign pattern and every of its superpatterns are spectrally arbitrary. This method worked for a sign pattern in whose class certain types of nilpotent matrices could be found. McDonald and Stuart [19] extended their method to the ray pattern case in the following manner:

The nilpotent-Jacobi method [19]:

1. Find a nilpotent matrix in the given ray pattern class.
2. Change $2n$ of the positive coefficients (denoted by r_1, r_2, \dots, r_{2n}) of the e^{ij} in this nilpotent matrix to variables t_1, t_2, \dots, t_{2n} .
3. Denote the characteristic polynomial of the resulting matrix as:

$$x^n + (f_1(t_1, \dots, t_{2n}) + ig_1(t_1, \dots, t_{2n}))x^{n-1} + \dots + (f_{n-1}(t_1, \dots, t_{2n}) + ig_{n-1}(t_1, \dots, t_{2n}))x + (f_n(t_1, \dots, t_{2n}) + ig_n(t_1, \dots, t_{2n}))$$

4. Find the Jacobi matrix

$$J = \frac{\partial(f_1, g_1, \dots, f_n, g_n)}{t_1, t_2, \dots, t_{2n}}$$

If the determinant of J evaluated at $(t_1, t_2, \dots, t_{2n}) = (r_1, r_2, \dots, r_{2n})$ is nonzero, then by continuity of the determinant in the entries of a matrix, there exists a neighborhood U of $(r_1, r_2, \dots, r_{2n})$ such that all the vectors in U are strictly positive and the determinant of J evaluated at any of these vectors is nonzero. Moreover, by the Implicit Function Theorem there is a neighborhood $V \subseteq U$ of $(r_1, r_2, \dots, r_{2n}) \subseteq \mathbb{R}^{2n}$, a neighborhood W of $(0, 0, \dots, 0) \subseteq \mathbb{R}^k$ and a function $(h_1, h_2, \dots, h_{2n})$ from W into V such that for any $(a_1, b_1, \dots, a_n, b_n) \in W$ there exists a strictly positive vector

$$(s_1, s_2, \dots, s_{2n}) = (h_1, h_2, \dots, h_{2n})(a_1, b_1, \dots, a_n, b_n) \in V$$

where $f_j(s_1, s_2, \dots, s_{2n}) = a_j$, $g_j(s_1, s_2, \dots, s_{2n}) = b_j$. If we take positive scalar multiples of the corresponding matrices, then we have that each monic n th degree polynomial over \mathbb{R} is the characteristic polynomial of some matrix in this ray pattern class.

5. Consider a superpattern of our pattern. Let $c_1 e^{\theta_1 \theta_n}$ be the new nonzero entries. Denote the new functions in characteristic polynomial by $\hat{F}(x)$. Let

$$\hat{F}(x) = x^n + \sum_{j=1}^n (\hat{f}_j(t_1, t_2, \dots, t_{2n}, c_1, \dots, c_k) + \hat{g}_j(t_1, t_2, \dots, t_{2n}, c_1, \dots, c_k))x^{n-j}$$

where $\hat{f}_j(t_1, t_2, \dots, t_{2n}, c_1, \dots, c_k)$ and $\hat{g}_j(t_1, t_2, \dots, t_{2n}, c_1, \dots, c_k)$ represent the real and complex parts of the coefficient of x^{n-j} . Let

$$\hat{J} = \frac{\partial(\hat{f}_1, \hat{g}_1, \dots, \hat{f}_n, \hat{g}_n)}{t_1, t_2, \dots, t_{2n}}$$

be the new Jacobi matrix. As above, let $(a_1, b_1, \dots, a_n, b_n) \in W$ and $(s_1, s_2, \dots, s_{2n}) = (h_1, h_2, \dots, h_{2n})(a_1, b_1, \dots, a_n, b_n) \in V$. Then

$$a_j = f_j(s_1, s_2, \dots, s_{2n}) = \hat{f}_j(s_1, s_2, \dots, s_{2n}, 0, \dots, 0) \\ b_j = g_j(s_1, s_2, \dots, s_{2n}) = \hat{g}_j(s_1, s_2, \dots, s_{2n}, 0, \dots, 0)$$

and the determinant of evaluated at

$$(t_1, t_2, \dots, t_{2n}, c_1, c_2, \dots, c_k) = (s_1, s_2, \dots, s_{2n}, 0, 0, \dots, 0)$$

is equal to the determinant of J evaluated at

$$(t_1, t_2, \dots, t_{2n}) = (s_1, s_2, \dots, s_{2n})$$

and hence is nonzero. By the implicit function theorem, there exists a neighborhood $\hat{V} \subseteq V$ of $(s_1, s_2, \dots, s_{2n})$, a neighborhood T of $(0, 0, \dots, 0) \in \mathbb{R}^k$ and a function $(q_1, q_2, \dots, q_{2n})$ from T into \hat{V} such that for any vector $(d_1, d_2, \dots, d_k) \in T$, there exists a strictly positive vector

$$(e_1, e_2, \dots, e_{2n}) = (q_1, q_2, \dots, q_{2n})(c_1, c_2, \dots, c_k) \in \hat{V}$$

where

$$\hat{f}_j(e_1, e_2, \dots, e_{2n}, c_1, c_2, \dots, c_k) = a_j$$

and

$$\hat{g}_j(e_1, e_2, \dots, e_{2n}, c_1, c_2, \dots, c_k) = b_j.$$

Taking $(d_1, d_2, \dots, d_k) \in T$ strictly positive, we have that there also exist matrices in the superpattern's class with every characteristic polynomial corresponding to a vector in W . If we choose positive scalar multiples of the corresponding matrices,

then we get that each monic n th degree polynomial over \mathbb{C} is the characteristic polynomial of some matrix in this superpattern's class.

III. MAIN RESULTS

In [18], McDonald and Stuart defined the $n \times n$ ray sign patterns of the following form.

$$A_n(\theta) = \begin{pmatrix} -1 & 1 & 0 & \cdots & \cdots & \cdots & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & e^{i\theta} & 1 & 0 & \cdots & \cdots & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & \cdots & 0 & 0 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \ddots & \ddots & \vdots & \vdots \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & \cdots & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ -1 & 0 & 0 & \cdots & \cdots & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ -1 & 1 & 0 & \cdots & \cdots & \cdots & 0 & 1 \\ 1 & -i & -i & \cdots & \cdots & \cdots & -i & -i \end{pmatrix} \quad (4)$$

where $0 \leq \theta \leq 2\pi$ and $n \geq 4$ and gave the following theorem.

Theorem1. [18] For $n \geq 4$, there exist infinitely many choices for θ with $0 \leq \theta \leq 2\pi$, so that $A_n(\theta)$ and all of its superpatterns are spectrally arbitrary ray patterns.

McDonald and Stuart [15] have proved the theorem. According to the definition of A_n .

$$A_4 = \begin{pmatrix} -1 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & e^{i\theta} & 1 & 0 \\ -1 & 1 & 0 & 1 \\ 1 & -i & -i & -i \end{pmatrix} \quad (5)$$

Unfortunately, we find that A_4 is not spectrally arbitrary for any θ with $0 \leq \theta \leq 2\pi$. Now we prove that A_4 is not spectrally arbitrary for any θ with $0 \leq \theta \leq 2\pi$. For convenience, we restrict θ to $0 \leq \theta \leq \frac{\pi}{2}$. Let $q = \cos \theta$.

Suppose $B_4 \in Q(A_4)$, then by scaling and positive diagonally similarity we can assume

$$B_4 = \begin{pmatrix} a_1 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ a_2 & q + i\sqrt{1-q^2} & 1 & 0 \\ a_3 & b_4 & 0 & 1 \\ a_4 & ib_3 & ib_2 & ib_1 \end{pmatrix} \quad (6)$$

where $a_1, a_2, a_3, b_1, b_2, b_3$ are negative and a_4, b_4 are positive. From [19], the characteristic polynomial of B_4 is as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} & x^4 + [(-a_1 - q) + i(-b_1 - \sqrt{1-q^2})]x^3 \\ & + [(-a_2 - b_1\sqrt{1-q^2} + a_1q - b_4) \\ & + i(-b_2 + a_1b_1 + a_1\sqrt{1-q^2} + b_1)]x^2 \\ & + [(-a_3 + a_1b_4 + a_1b_1\sqrt{1-q^2} - b_2\sqrt{1-q^2}) \\ & + i(-b_3 - a_1b_1q + b_2q + \sum_{k=1}^2 a_k b_{3-k} + b_1b_4)]x \\ & + [-a_4 + a_1b_2\sqrt{1-q^2} \\ & + i(-a_1b_1b_4 - a_1b_2q + \sum_{k=1}^3 a_k b_{4-k})] \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

Suppose that B_4 is nilpotent. Setting the coefficient of x^{n-j} equal to zero for $j=1,2,3,4$, then solving for a_j and b_j , we get that

$$\begin{aligned} a_1 &= -q, \\ b_1 &= -\sqrt{1-q^2}, \\ a_2 &= b_1\sqrt{1-q^2} + a_1q - b_4 \\ &= q\sqrt{1-q^2}, \\ a_3 &= a_1b_4 + a_1b_1\sqrt{1-q^2} - b_2\sqrt{1-q^2} \\ &= -qb_4 + 2q(1-q^2), \\ b_3 &= -a_1b_1q + b_2q + \sum_{k=1}^2 a_k b_{3-k} + b_1b_4 \\ &= -(1-q^2)\sqrt{1-q^2}, \\ a_4 &= a_1b_2\sqrt{1-q^2} = q^2(1-q^2), \\ b_4 &= \frac{-a_1b_2q + a_1b_3 + (1-2q^2)b_2 + 2q(1-q^2)b_1}{b_2} \\ &= 2(1-q^2) \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

Substituting b_4 into the equation

$$a_3 = qb_4 + 2q(1-q^2) \quad (9)$$

we obtain

$$a_3 = -2q(1-q^2) + 2q(1-q^2) = 0 \quad (10)$$

which contradicts the fact that $B_4 \in Q(A_4)$. Thus, A_4 is not potentially nilpotent, which implies that A_4 is not spectrally arbitrary for any θ with $0 \leq \theta \leq 2\pi$.

IV. EXAMPLES

Example1. The 4×4 ray pattern

$$A = \begin{pmatrix} -1 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & \frac{1+\sqrt{3}i}{2} & 1 & 0 \\ -1 & 1 & 0 & 1 \\ 1 & -i & -i & -i \end{pmatrix} \quad (11)$$

is not spectrally arbitrary. The matrix

$$B = \begin{pmatrix} a_1 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ a_2 & \frac{1+\sqrt{3}i}{2} & 1 & 0 \\ a_3 & b_4 & 0 & 1 \\ a_4 & ib_3 & ib_2 & ib_1 \end{pmatrix} \quad (12)$$

is in the pattern class $B \in Q(A)$ whenever a_2, a_4 are negative and a_1, a_3, b_1, b_2, b_3 are positive. The characteristic polynomial of B is

$$\begin{aligned} & x^4 + [(a_1 - \frac{1}{2}) + i(-b_1 - \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2})]x^3 \\ & + [(-a_2 - \frac{\sqrt{3}b_1}{2} + \frac{a_1}{2} - b_4) \\ & + i(-b_2 + a_1b_1 + \frac{\sqrt{3}a_1}{2} - \frac{b_1}{2})]x^2 \\ & + [(-a_3 + a_1b_4 + \frac{\sqrt{3}a_1b_1}{2} - \frac{\sqrt{3}b_2}{2}) \\ & + i(-b_3 - \frac{a_1b_1}{2} + \frac{b_2}{2} + \sum_{k=1}^2 a_k b_{3-k} + b_1b_4)]x \\ & + [(-a_4 + \frac{\sqrt{3}a_1b_2}{2}) + i(-a_1b_1b_4 - \frac{a_1b_2}{2} + \sum_{k=1}^3 a_k b_{4-k})] \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

Suppose that B is nilpotent. Setting the coefficient of x^{n-j} equal to zero for $j = 1, 2, 3, 4$, then solving for a_j and b_j , we get that

$$\begin{aligned} a_1 &= -\frac{1}{2}, a_2 = -1, a_3 = 0, a_4 = \frac{3}{16}, \\ b_1 &= -\frac{\sqrt{3}}{2}, b_2 = -\frac{\sqrt{3}}{4}, b_3 = -\frac{3\sqrt{3}}{8}, b_4 = \frac{3}{16} \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

which contradicts the fact that $B \in Q(A)$. Thus, A is not potentially nilpotent, which implies that A is not spectrally arbitrary.

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